

Mapping the dynamic of research in the OIC region

Pr. Lrhoul H. School of Information Sciences. Rabat

Pr. Hammouti B. Faculty of Science, University Mohammed
Premier. Oujda

May 11th, 2023

Context

- 90% of scientific output is produced by developed countries (US, china, UK, GERMANY, INDIA, JAPAN);
- The two countries with the highest output are China (23%) and the US (16%);
- The 57 Islamic countries contribute with (8.29%) to the world science;
- Members of the OIC have not been able to reach the UNESCO target of investing 1% of their national GDP in R&D;
- Absence of national research policies in the OIC countries to address local problems

Objectives

The objective is to analyze the research landscape of 6 members of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (Turkey, Iran, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Egypt and Morocco).

The study provides an overview of scientific productivity, identifies the main characteristics and trends of international collaboration during the period 2011-2021

Methodology

Scientometric indicators allow decision makers to guide their research policy, invest in national priorities, develop international collaborations

We collect bibliographic data from the countries in the Islamic world that have the highest number of publications between 2011 and 2021.

We used data from the scopus database and SCImago Journal and Country Rank (SJR).

OIC member countries have increased the allocation for research and development (R&D) and enhanced international collaboration

Data by country

Evolution of Scientific production Turkey, Iran, Malaysia, SA, Egypt & Morocco

Source: Scimagojr

Impact of Scientific production

The impact of publications from the Islamic world remains very low compared to the developed countries, especially in international research topics (Biochemistry, Genetics, Molecular Biology, Economics, Neurosciences)

Dentistry, Energy and engineering are the top three fields that account for 25% of the world's output in terms of citations.

Impact of Scientific production

Research impact in Biochemistry, Genetic, Molecular Biology (3625 per year) and Chemical engineering (2824) is the highest in Iran, followed by Saudi Arabia;

The citation of articles in economic and business does not exceed 700 per year.

Research thematic

In the Islamic world, the output of veterinary research is in the lead, followed by chemical engineering, chemistry, dentistry, agricultural and biological sciences, mathematics, pharmacy.

Saudi Arabia was the leader in materials science research followed by Malaysia, Iran, and Pakistan.

Efforts should be deployed to develop research in the field of energy, especially in Iran and Malaysia.

Sarwar, R., & Hassan, S. U. (2015). A bibliometric assessment of scientific productivity and international collaboration of the Islamic World in science and technology (S&T) areas. *Scientometrics*, 105(2), 1059-1077.

Haq, I. U., & Tanveer, M. (2020). Status of research productivity and higher education in the members of Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC). *Library Philosophy and Practice (ejournal)*, 3845.

International collaboration

The most productive countries i (Turkey, Iran, Malaysia), have a limited network of collaboration with other Islamic countries.

It is necessary to increase the collaboration among the OIC member countries.

Scientific journals

Conclusion

- Define a national research strategy;
 - Provide researchers with adequate work environment, equipment and financing for R&D;
 - Develop cooperation among OIC members in publishing, validation of articles, creation of regional journals are ways to improve the impact of research in the region
-

THANK YOU